

Understanding Heat-Induced Liquid Crystal Display Failures

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Abstract – Liquid Crystal Displays (LCDs) have become abundant in modern technology, powering everything from smartphones and TVs to automotive infotainment systems and digital signage. Their popularity stems from their lightweight design, energy efficiency, and ability to produce sharp, bright, and vibrant images. However, as with any technology, LCDs are not immune to failure. Prolonged exposure to certain environmental and operational stresses can compromise their performance and longevity. [1] [2] One of the primary challenges Liquid Crystal Displays (LCDs) face is heat. Higher temperatures can disrupt the precise alignment of liquid crystals, deform critical structural components of the screen, and accelerate degradation of the backlight system. This paper aims to shed light on the science behind how Liquid Crystal Displays are affected by different temperatures and environments, more specifically what happens when you heat liquid crystals above their clearing point and the degradation effects of UV light.

Keywords – LCD, Liquid Crystals, Isotropic Transition, Digital Signage, Failures, Nematic Crystalline Solids

I. INTRODUCTION TO LCDS

Typical Thin-Film Transistor (TFT) LCDs work by modulating the passage of light through polarization. In twisted nematic (TN) applications, light first passes through a rear polarizing filter and then interacts with the twisted alignment of the liquid crystals, which modulate and adjust its polarization. This polarized light continues through the color filter and then the adjusted polarization of the light determines whether it is blocked by, or transmitted through, the front polarizing filter. This light modulation forms the visible image on the display. Additional operation modes include Fringe-field Switching (FFS), In-Plane Switching (IPS), and Vertical Alignment (VA). [3]

Liquid crystals (LC) typically must be in their anisotropic liquid (nematic) phase to be useful in displays. The nematic phase is where the LCs anisotropic alignment can be manipulated by modulating small electrical fields within each pixel. This allows the liquid crystals to control the polarization of light effectively. There are many different LC structures, and it is important to know the LCs nematic temperature range. For example: 4-Cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) is a widely used liquid crystal material as a standard in LCD studies and its nematic range is 74°F to 96°F. Additionally, 4-(trans-4-Pentylcyclohexyl)benzointrile (PCH5) has a nematic range of 85°F and 130°F. [4] [5] [6]

Fig.1. Layers of a typical Thin Film Transistor LCD Panel
1) Glass Substrates 2) Rear Polarizer
3) Front Polarizer 4) Color Filter 5) TFTs
6) Liquid Crystals 7) Electrode Layers 8) Spacers

II. EXCEEDING THE LC'S NEMATIC RANGE

When liquid crystals exceed their nematic temperature range, known as the clearing point (TNI), they transition into an isotropic phase. In this state, liquid crystals lose their anisotropic alignment properties, behaving like ordinary liquids. This loss of alignment disrupts their ability to control light, resulting in black or dark spots on the display. [6] Imagine a Jenga® tower carefully built, with all the blocks stacked neatly so the structure stands tall and strong. Now, think about what happens when someone bumps the table hard. The blocks lose their alignment, tumble over, and the tower collapses into a chaotic pile. The isotropic phase in an LCD is like that: the liquid crystals are the neatly stacked Jenga blocks, and heat is the bump that disrupts their careful arrangement and no longer able to adjust the light's polarization.

If the temperature remains excessively high or these transitions occur too frequently, the liquid crystals can degrade permanently, becoming permanently isotropic. This irreversible damage renders the affected areas of the screen non-functional and will require the entire display to be replaced. [7]

It is also important to note that liquid crystals can operate at temperatures lower than their optimal range, entering a crystalline or smectic phase. In this state, the molecular movement becomes slower, which reduces the response time of the liquid crystals. As a result, the display may exhibit a “ghosting” effect, where previous images linger briefly before fading. [6]

Fig.2. Visualization of the Smectic, Nematic, and Isotropic phases of Liquid Crystals

III. SUBSTRATE AND SPACER DEFORMATION

The glass substrates in LCDs serve as the structural foundation that sandwiches the liquid crystal layer. These substrates, along with microscopic spacers, maintain a precise cell gap, typically around 5 microns. [8] This cell gap is critical for ensuring the uniform alignment of liquid crystals and consistent image quality, as even minor deviations can lead to noticeable distortions.

However, when exposed to elevated temperatures, the materials used in the substrates and spacers can suffer from thermal expansion. Glass and plastic substrates expand at different rates depending on their thermal properties, which can cause warping or unevenness in the panel. The spacers, which are typically spherical and commonly made of silica or plastic, are also vulnerable to heat, compromising their ability to maintain the uniform cell gap. Prolonged exposure to high temperatures can soften or deform these spacers. Plastic spacers are particularly prone to softening, and even silica spacers can degrade under extreme thermal conditions. [9]

As a result, the liquid crystal layer itself is affected. Variations in the cell gap disrupt the precise alignment of the liquid crystals, impairing their ability to effectively modulate light. This misalignment leads to a range of visual distortions, including bright or dark spots where the liquid crystal cannot block or transmit light properly. Circular voids can also be present where liquid crystals are absent due to the expansion of the cell gap. [8] [9]

The consequences of these thermal effects are not just immediate but can also be long-lasting. Repeated exposure to high temperatures or constant thermal cycling accelerates the degradation of both substrates and spacers. Over time, or under extreme temperatures, this can result in permanent deformation that renders portions of the display, or even the entire panel, non-functional.

Heat management and the use of materials with higher thermal stability are critical for minimizing the risk of substrate and spacer deformation in LCDs. By understanding the temperature limits of each component, manufacturers and users alike can ensure better longevity and performance.

Fig.3. Trapped void due to substrate warping under extreme heat.

Fig.3.1. Applying pressure to and area adjacent to void relocates the failure.

IV. BACKLIGHT AND EDGE-LIGHT FAILURES

The backlight unit (BLU) is where all visible light for the display originates. For optimal performance, the BLU must operate consistently, but heat and prolonged usage can lead to backlight failures, ultimately affecting display quality, brightness, and reliability.

One major issue affecting backlight units is thermal aging, a gradual process that reduces brightness and color accuracy over time. In LED backlights, thermal stress degrades the internal phosphors responsible for producing light, causing the display to appear dimmer and less vibrant. While these effects develop slowly, they are inevitable without effective heat management, which can significantly shorten the lifespan of the display. [10]

Additionally, LED edge-lighting systems, which are popular for their application in thin displays, introduce more specific challenges. These systems often create localized thermal hot zones, particularly near the bottom edge of the display. Uneven heating and cooling cycles in these zones can lead to cracks in the diffusion panel and will appear as bright vertical streaks. To mitigate this, using thermally stable materials for reflectors and diffusion panels is a must.

The driver board, which regulates the backlight's power supply, is another weak point prone to heat-related failures. Prolonged thermal stress can lead to voltage instability, intermittent failures, or even complete breakdowns. Without adequate cooling, the strain on the driver board can result in cascading failures, further impacting the display's performance.

Preventing backlight failures requires a combination of thermal management strategies and the use of components with enhanced thermal stability. By addressing these challenges, manufacturers can delay the effects of thermal aging, improve longevity, and ensure consistent display quality throughout the product's lifespan.

V. ULTRAVIOLET DEGRADATION

Ultraviolet (UV) radiation is another environmental factor that can lead to LCD failures, particularly in outdoor or high-sunlight applications. Prolonged exposure to UV light can chemically and physically degrade the materials in an LCD, ultimately modifying its optical performance and structural integrity.

One of the most vulnerable components to UV damage is the polarizing filters. These filters control the light passing through the display to form images. Over time, exposure to UV radiation can break down the chemical bonds within the filters, leading to yellowing or discoloration. This degradation reduces the display's brightness and contrast. In severe cases, UV exposure can cause the filters to delaminate or peel, further damaging their optical properties. Similarly, UV radiation also affects the backlight system's reflectors and diffusion panels, which can discolor or warp over time. This results in uneven light distribution across the screen, diminishing the overall image quality. [11]

Liquid crystals themselves are also affected by UV radiation. Prolonged UV exposure can alter their molecular structure. This not only accelerates isotropic transitions but can also result in permanent molecular damage, rendering parts of the display inoperable. [11]

Protective layers, like anti-UV films, can also be integrated into the display design, while recommendations for installation in shaded or indirect sunlight locations further reduce exposure.

VI. MATERIAL INNOVATION

As with most other technologies, LCDs are advancing. The adoption of heat-resistant liquid crystal formulations and high-quality substrates with low thermal expansion coefficients are enabling more LCD screens to be suitable for use in direct sunlight, even in very hot environments. BOE has developed a liquid crystal material (BHR95300) for use in FFS-TFT displays and has a very wide nematic range with a low of -22°F and a clearing point of 199.4°F [12]. While FFS-TFT is more commonly associated with small to medium-sized displays, advancements in manufacturing and demand for high-quality visuals have enabled its use in larger formats.

MiniLED and MicroLED backlights enhance LCD performance with higher brightness, better contrast, and improved energy efficiency. MiniLEDs are cost-effective and provide uniform light, while MicroLEDs offer superior HDR control but at higher costs. Corner-lit MiniLEDs balance performance and affordability, minimizing thermal hotspots. Both technologies resist UV damage and operate cooler than traditional CCFLs, extending durability. [13]

VII. CONCLUSION

When selecting the appropriate LCD screen, the decision should begin with a thorough consideration of its intended use case and environmental conditions. Factors such as exposure to heat, UV radiation, and operational stresses must be considered to ensure the longevity and reliability of the display. For environments with high thermal or UV exposure, opting for displays with advanced materials, such as heat-resistant liquid crystals, UV-filters, and robust backlight systems, can mitigate failure risks. Furthermore, proper thermal management through efficient cooling systems and strategic placement of displays in shaded environments or under a canopy can significantly enhance performance and durability.

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Yi Lu, PhD – BOE adds: “We couldn’t agree more that thermal management at the system level is critical to outdoor LCD devices. UV protection is significant to the overall reliability. Our panels are tested in chambers to simulate ambient temperature and humidity levels, but solar loading in the real world causes additional challenges. Our empirical data indicates that operating under direct sunlight at $\sim 60^{\circ}\text{C}$ ambient temperature can easily make the LCD surface temperature to $\sim 80^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is the upper limit for most polarizers.”

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